

**The intermittent MERS-CoV outbreaks between 2012 and 2019: a
premonition of the COVID-19 pandemic**

Libing Shen^{1*}

Author Affiliations:

¹ International Human Phenome Institutes (Shanghai), Shanghai, 200433, P.R. China

* Corresponding author: Libing Shen, Email: shenlibing@ihup.org.cn

Abstract

Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV) has an almost identical clinical spectrum as severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). Their phylogenetic trees rooted with their closest bat coronaviruses exhibit that MERS-CoVs and SARS-CoV-2s display the same rapid expansion, although bat coronaviruses are too distant to serve as the proper outgroups in both cases. The similarities between MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 are too striking to be ignored. In this study, we used a published method to search the least mutated sequence in 497 MERS-CoV complete genomes. According to parsimony principle, the least mutated sequence is the phylogenetic root in a sequence alignment. Interestingly, the least mutated MERS-CoV sequence found in our dataset was collected from a dromedary camel in 2015 when the virus had been identified for three years. Our further analysis shows the least mutated MERS-CoV is evolutionarily very close to MERS-CoV common ancestor which is the actual phylogenetic root of MERS-CoVs. We also reconstructed the putative MERS-CoV common ancestor sequence whose phylogenetic position in the MERS-CoV tree is the same as the lineage B.1 SARS-CoV-2's phylogenetic position in the SARS-CoV-2 tree. Thus, we infer that MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 are the results of two recent viral speciation events. Evidently, the intermittent MERS-CoV outbreaks between 2012 and 2019 should be due to the multiple introductions of a single MERS-CoV ancestor. The example of MERS-CoV is a premonition for us that SARS-CoV-2 could haunt human for decades unless we find its true origin. The evolutionary mechanisms underlying MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 may provide us some insights for the future disease X.

Introduction

Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV) is a pathogenic beta-coronavirus first reported in Middle East in 2012 (1). This virus imposes a serious threat to human health. Its symptoms include fever, cough, diarrhea, and pneumonia (2). Frighteningly, MERS-CoV has an overall death rate of 34% in human hosts (3). Since its appearance, MERS-CoV has spread to more than 25 countries and four major continents (Asia, Europe, Africa, and North America) (3). Fortunately, due to its relatively low sustained human-to-human transmissibility, the population influenced by MERS-CoV is confined to a very small number.

The typical coding region of MERS-CoV's genome has 29529 nucleotides in length and is 120 nucleotides longer than that of SARS-CoV-2's genome (1, 4). Both viruses belong to beta-coronavirus family and also share a similar genomic structure, which contains seven predicted open reading frames (ORFs) and four structural genes – spike (S), envelope (E), membrane (M), and nucleocapsid (N) (5). However, unlike MERS-CoV, SARS-CoV-2 is highly contagious and renders the world still in the midst of COVID-19 pandemic (6).

So far, the origins of MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 are yet unknown. Some evidence shows that MER-CoV-related viruses might have existed in central and east Africa for decades (7, 8). Many mammals host MER-CoV-related viruses in their natural habitats, including two species of bats (*Neoromicia capensis* and *Vespertilio superans*), dromedary camel (*Camelus dromedarius*), and European hedgehog (*Erinaceus europaeus*) (9-13). SARS-CoV-2-like viruses were also reported in bats (14). Now the question is whether these two viruses have circulated in their natural hosts for years before infected human beings or just recently emerged.

In this study, we systematically investigated the origin of MER-CoVs using a published method to search the least mutated sequence in a MERS-CoVs' genome alignment. According to parsimony principle, the least mutated sequence should the

phylogenetic root to the other sequences in an alignment. Our results show that the intermittent MERS-CoV outbreaks between 2012 and 2019 is actually due to the multiple introductions of a single MERS-CoV ancestor. Since SARS-CoV-2 resembles MERS-CoV in many ways, the MERS-CoV's results may provide some cues for the development of SARS-CoV-2 outbreak in the future. The World Health Organization adopts the term "Disease X" for the future outbreaks and pandemics caused by an unknown pathogen. We hope that our evolutionary analyses of MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 could give the world a glimpse of where disease X might come from.

Materials and Methods

MERS-CoV genome data

We retrieved the MERS-CoV genome data from NCBI Nucleotide database using the keys of MERS-CoV and complete genome. We used an in-house Perl script to filter the MERS-CoV genome sequence shorter than 29000 nucleotides or with ambiguous site (such as N).

SARS -CoV-2 genome data

The SARS-CoV data used in this study were directly adopted from our previous paper (15). The URL for our previous paper is: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10645490>.

Complete coding region extraction for MERS-CoV sequences

We used the whole coding region of the MERS-CoV collected on June 13, 2012 (NCBI accession ID: JX869059.2) as the reference template to extract the complete coding region for the filtered MERS-CoV genome sequences (16). The length of JX869059.2's whole coding region is 29529 nucleotides. Each MERS-CoV genome sequence was aligned to the whole coding region of JX869059. We used MUSCLE 3.8.31 to perform the alignment with default parameters (17). The sequence with incomplete opening reading frame, deletion or insertion according to JX869059.2 was excluded from this study. The MERS-CoV related genome sequences isolated from

bat species were not subjected to the filter process above.

Global point mutation calculation

In this study, we used a published method to calculate the number of global point mutations in a MERS-CoV genome sequence alignment and find the least mutated MERS-CoV sequence (18). Each sequence was pair-wisely compared with the other sequences in the final MERS-CoV alignment and the number of point mutations from each comparison was summed up. By doing so, one can obtain the number of global point mutations for each sequence. According to parsimony principle, the root sequence should have the least number of global point mutations.

Pairwise distance calculation and phylogenetic analyses

Pairwise distances for nucleotide difference among MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 sequences was calculated with MEGA X (19). The phylogenetic trees of MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 were also constructed using neighbor-joining method with gamma distributed rates in MEGA X (19).

Result

The similar topologies of the rooted MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 phylogenetic trees

The polygenetic tree of MERS-CoV was constructed with 40 MERS-CoV sequences (collected in 2012 and 2013) and rooted with three outgroup sequences (**Figure 1A**). The polygenetic tree of SARS-CoV-2 was constructed with 52 large SARS-CoV-2 strains (with more 200 sequences) and rooted with two outgroup sequences (**Figure 1B**). Both trees show a very similar topology relative to the outgroup sequences. The branches of MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 taxonomic units in both trees are very short, which exhibit a very rapid expansion mode.

Notably, the outgroup sequences are distant to the main tree in both MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 trees. It indicates that even the closest bat outgroups are not proper for

inferring the evolutionary relationships within MERS-CoVs or SARS-CoV-2s due to the long branch attraction effect.

The nucleotide difference between the outgroups and MERS-CoVs/SARS-CoV-2s

The phylogenetic analyses show that the evolutionary distance within MERS-CoVs or SARS-CoV-2s is short. In order to have a clear view of the evolutionary distance between the outgroup sequences and MERS-CoVs/SARS-CoV-2s, we calculated the nucleotide difference between the outgroups and MERS-CoVs/SARS-CoV-2s (**Table 1 and 2**). Table 1 shows that the average nucleotide difference between the closest outgroup (KC869678.4) and seven MERS-CoVs is 4147 nucleotides while the nucleotide differences among MERS-CoVs are from 10 to 157 nucleotides. Table 2 shows that the average nucleotide difference between the closest outgroup (BANAL-20-52) and eight SARS-CoV-2s is 905 nucleotides while the nucleotide differences among SARS-CoV-2s are from 1 to 13 nucleotides. Thus, in both MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 cases, the closest group sequence is an order of magnitude different from ingroups in term of nucleotide distance (4147 vs. 157 in MERS-CoV and 905 vs. 13 in SARS-CoV-2).

The least mutated sequence among MERS-CoVs

We calculated the least mutated sequence in 497 MERS-CoV sequences with complete coding region. The result shows that the least mutated sequence is a MERS-CoV sequence (MF598664.1) collected from camel in Mar, 2015. Theoretically, it should be the ancestor to all MERS-CoV sequences in our dataset. However, MERS-CoV was first identified in 2012 (1). It seems counterintuitive that an ancestor appeared three years later than its descendants.

To further check this result, we first calculated the least mutated MERS-CoV sequence by year. From 2012 to 2019, there are eight least mutated MERS-CoV sequences, one for each year (supplemental data). MF598664.1 is still the least

mutated MERS-CoV sequence in the year of 2015. Second, we calculated the least mutated MERS-CoV sequence among eight least mutated MERS-CoV sequences from 2012 to 2019. Again, MF598664.1 is the least mutated MERS-CoV sequence in this sub-dataset.

The unrooted phylogenetic trees of the least mutated MERS-CoV sequences of different years and the major SARS-CoV-2 strains

To examine the phylogenetic relationship of the least mutated MERS-CoV sequences of different years, we constructed an unrooted phylogenetic tree for them (**Figure 2**). The tree shows that MF598664.1 is closer to the root position than the other MERS-CoV sequences. In comparison, we also constructed an unrooted phylogenetic tree for the major SARS-CoV-2 strains including lineage B.1 (the major SARS-CoV-2 strain has at least 200 sequences in our SARS-CoV-2 dataset). **Figure 3A** shows that MF598664.1 is closer to the center of the unrooted MERS-CoV tree. **Figure 3B** shows that lineage B.1 (strain-1) is at the center of the unrooted SARS-CoV-2 tree. The result further confirms that the major branches of SARS-CoV-2 was stemmed from the lineage B.1.

Reconstruction of MERS-CoV common ancestor

Our phylogenetic analysis demonstrates that MF598664.1 is very close to the root position, although it is not the root. This result indicates that MF598664.1 is not the common ancestor to all MERS-CoVs. Using parsimony method, we inferred the putative common ancestor for all MERS-CoVs. It has six nucleotide differences from MF598664.1 (**Table 3**). None of them locates in spike protein. Finally, we constructed a phylogenetic tree rooted with the putative MERS-CoV common ancestor (**Figure 4**), whose position is the same as strain-1's position in the SARS-CoV-2 phylogenetic analysis.

Discussion

The similarities and differences between MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2

Both MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 belong to the beta-coronavirus genus. They exhibit the striking similarities in symptoms, transmission pattern, and phylogenetic feature. MERS-CoV has typical symptoms as fever, cough, fatigue, diarrhea and pneumonia (2). SARS-CoV-2 has exactly the same typical symptoms (20). They both also have asymptomatic cases (21). MERS-CoV is capable of long-distance airborne transmission and SARS-CoV-2 as well (22, 23). The phylogenetic analyses of MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 show that they have a similar evolutionary pattern of rapid expansion as their emergence.

The conspicuous difference between MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 is that MERS-CoV's mortality rate is an order of magnitude higher than that of SARS-CoV-2 while SARS-CoV-2's mutation rate is an order of magnitude lower than that of MERS-CoV (2, 18, 24). We don't know whether the mortality rate is associated with the mutation rate in beta-coronaviruses. It appears that this probable correlation is worth investigating in the future.

The closet outgroup and the possible birthplace of coronavirus

The average nucleotide difference between the closest outgroup (KC869678.4) and MERS-CoVs is much greater than the average nucleotide difference between the closest outgroup (BANAL-20-52) and SARS-CoV-2s (4147 vs. 905 nucleotides). However, the nucleotide differences among SARS-CoV-2s are about 10 times less than those among MERS-CoVs. It is another evidence that SARS-CoV-2's evolutionary rate is an order of magnitude slower than MERS-CoV's. Thus, the phylogenetic trees show that the closest outgroup is more distant to SARS-CoV-2s than to MERS-CoVs, although the average nucleotide difference between the closest outgroup (BANAL-20-52) and SARS-CoV-2s is much smaller.

KC869678.4 is collected in South Africa while MERS-CoVs repeatedly appeared in Middle East (1, 3). They are found in two different continents. BANAL-20-52 is collected in Laos and the birthplace of SARS-CoV-2s is still unknown (14). The

example of MERS-CoVs proposes that using the closest outgroup to assert SARS-CoV-2's place of origin is more than inaccurate.

MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 are from two recent viral speciation events

The similarities between MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 argue that they are extremely unlikely to be a result of human design. Our analyses further show that they both stemmed from a single virus sequence. Thus, MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 are a product of nature and created by two recent viral speciation events.

We notice that there is a trend of short insertions and deletions in beta-coronavirus genomes. SARS-CoV-1 is the first identified human-pathogenic beta-coronavirus in this century (25). Human SARS-CoV-1s have a short deletion (29 nucleotides) in its genome compared with their civet counterpart (26). Short insertions can be also observed in MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2. The closest beta-coronavirus to MERS-CoV found so far is KC869678.4 which has a genomic coding region of 29521 nucleotides. The closest beta-coronavirus to SARS-CoV-2 found so far is BANAL-20-52 which has a genomic coding region of 29370 nucleotides. MERS-CoV has a typical complete genomic coding region of 29529 nucleotides and SARS-CoV-2 has a typical complete genomic coding region of 29409 nucleotides, both of which are a little bit longer than their closest animal counterparts. Notably, Omicron variant as the most prevailing successor of the original SARS-CoV-2 has a typical genomic coding region of 29379 nucleotides (GISAID ID: EPI_ISL_6640917). Its genomic coding region has 39-nucleotide deletion and 9-nucleotide insertion compared with the lineage B.1.

If the hypothesis of short insertions and deletions for new coronavirus genome creation is correct, we speculate that the Omicron genome may be the optimal result of SARS-CoV-2 genome's fine tuning and the Omicron variant infection is the second wave of COVID-19 pandemic. If the Omicron genome could be further optimized, deletion and insertion would be at a single-digit level, which is very difficult to

achieve through a random process. It is a hopeful sign that the COVID-19 pandemic will end in 2024.

The circulation of beta-coronaviruses among bat species

The position of the common ancestors on the phylogenetic tree are rather nodes than branches (**Figure 5**'s top left legend). Usually, it is difficult to collect ancestral sequences, because they are confined to a very limited time window and space area. As time passes by, the collected taxon sequences are descendants. However, in cases of MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2, their fast expansion modes provide the rare opportunity to identify their ancestral sequences, or at least the sequences closest to the ancestor node. SARS-CoV-2 is a special example even among viruses for its extremely slow evolutionary rate. Some SARS-CoV-2 strains can last nearly a year and half until they exhaust the potential infected population. SARS-CoV-2's slow evolutionary capability may lie in its nonstructural protein 14 (nsp 14) which is essential for replication fidelity in coronavirus (27). Their wide-spread and long-lasting features made collecting and inferring the SARS-CoV-2's ancestral sequences possible.

There still exists the question of where the virus ancestor came from, even if it has been identified. The MERS-CoV-related coronaviruses found in bats may give some clues on this question. Coronaviruses are known to be able to jump across species (28). The phylogenetic analysis of MERS-CoVs and their related coronaviruses shows that the MERS-CoV-related coronaviruses were collected from different bat species spanning a long period of time and covering a large geographic area (**Figure 5**). These MERS-CoV-related coronaviruses must descend from a common ancestor in bat. It is conceivable that MERS-CoV was an outcome of a long past coronavirus circulation among different bat species. First, the ancestral virus jumped across different bat species. Second, it evolved to jump across different mammal species. Last, one of its descendants triggered the disease outbreak in human. Perhaps, MERS-CoV-related coronaviruses are just the relics of this past bat coronavirus circulation. Now the

World Health Organization coins the term “Disease X” for the future outbreaks and pandemics caused by an unknown pathogen. Our analyses of the evolutionary mechanisms underlying MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 could provide some thoughts for the scientific community around the world how disease X might emerge.

Data availability

The data and results of this study can be downloaded from <https://github.com/libing-shen/Least-mutated-sequence/tree/main/mers-cov>.

Compliance and ethics

All authors declare no potential competing interest. This work used the online data and ethical approval is not applicable.

Author’s contributions

LBS collected and analyzed the data. LBS wrote and revised the manuscript.

Consent for publication

The author consented the right for publication.

Competing interests

The author declares no potential competing interest.

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Figure 2. The unrooted neighbor-join tree of eight least mutated MERS-CoV sequences by different year from 2012 to 2019. The tree is drawn to scale and the scale bar represents the nucleotide differences.

Figure 3. The unrooted neighbor-join trees of MERS-CoVs and SARS-CoV-2s. **A.** The unrooted neighbor-join tree of eight least mutated MERS-CoV sequences by different year from 2012 to 2019. The red filled circle ● indicates the center (phylogenetic root) of the tree. The green filled cycle ● indicates the MERS-CoV sequence (MF598664.1) closest to the phylogenetic root. **B.** The unrooted neighbor-join tree of 54 SARS-CoV-2 strains. The red filled cycle ● indicates strain-1 (lineage B.1). The green filled cycle ● indicate strain-7329 (lineage B). The light blue filled cycle ● indicates strain-28468 (proCoV2). The dark filled cycle ● indicates strain-21397 (lineage A). The tree is drawn to scale and the scale bar represents the evolutionary distance.

Figure 4. The rooted neighbor-join trees of nine MERS-CoV sequences. The putative MERS-CoV common ancestor serves as the outgroup to root the tree. The red filled circle ● shows the putative MERS-CoV common ancestor. The green filled circle ● shows the MERS-CoV sequence (MF598664.1) closest to the phylogenetic root. The tree is drawn to scale and the scale bar represents the nucleotide differences. The number before each taxon indicates its nucleotide differences compared with MERS-CoV common ancestor.

Figure 5. The neighbor-join tree of MERS-CoVs and MERS-CoV-related coronaviruses rooted with OK572989.1. The diamond represents MERS-CoV-related coronaviruses. \diamond The hollowed diamond indicates that the taxon has no host information. The filled color diamond indicates the taxon has host bat species information. The up-left legend shows the evolutionary sketch for MERS-CoVs and MERS-CoV-related coronaviruses.

Tables:

Table 1. The pairwise nucleotide differences among the outgroups and MERS-CoVs.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1. MG596803.1		347	6966	6850	6858	6855	6856	6855	6855
2. MG596802.1	347		6960	6839	6846	6844	6845	6842	6842
3. KC869678.4	6966	6960		4155	4157	4147	4141	4142	4142
4. KJ477103.2	6850	6839	4155		137	140	155	155	157
5. JX869059.2	6858	6846	4157	137		83	100	100	100
6. KF600652.1	6855	6844	4147	140	83		41	45	47
7. KJ713298.1	6856	6845	4141	155	100	41		34	36
8. KJ713296.1	6855	6842	4142	155	100	45	34		10
9. KJ713295.1	6855	6842	4142	157	100	47	36	10	

Note: 1, 2 and 3 are bat MERS-CoV-related coronaviruses serving as the outgroups in phylogenetic analysis. 4-9 are MERS-CoVs.

Table 2. The pairwise nucleotide differences among the outgroups and SARS-CoV-2s.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1. RaTG13		1179	1137	1136	1134	1134	1134	1136	1135
2. BANAL-20-52	1179		908	907	906	903	905	899	906
3. strain-76949	1137	908		1	13	11	11	13	10
4. strain-61958	1136	907	1		12	10	10	12	9
5. strain-91923	1134	906	13	12		10	8	12	11
6. strain-60840	1134	903	11	10	10		8	10	9
7. strain-61209	1134	905	11	10	8	8		10	9
8. strain-75305	1136	899	13	12	12	10	10		11
9. strain-50498	1135	906	10	9	11	9	9	11	

Note: 1 and 2 are bat SARS-CoV-2-like coronaviruses serving as the outgroups in phylogenetic analysis. 3-9 are human SARS-CoV-2s.

Table 3. The nucleotide differences between the putative MERS-CoV common ancestor and MF598664.1.

Position in genome*	MERS-CoV common ancestor	MF598664.1	Function type	Amino acid change (gene)
6357	G	T	non-synonymous	M2119I (orf1ab1)
7023	C	T	synonymous	NA
14960	T	C	synonymous	NA
24105	C	T	synonymous	NA
25648	C	T	synonymous	NA
25877	G	C	non-synonymous	E101Q (NS4A)

*Position in genome starts from the first codon.